

EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP CHANGE IN POLICY AND GOVERNANCE: A PANACEA FOR SCHOOL INITIATIVES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: In the Nigerian education system, organizational change is frequently misconstrued as being driven by individual or group preferences. This article aims to delve into various pieces of literature to explore how change leadership in policies and governance can be effectively implemented in schools to foster innovation. Employing a meta-framework design approach, the article thoroughly reviews change leadership domains. A synthesis of peer-reviewed journals is presented to elucidate the nexus between leadership philosophy, change, and innovations within Nigerian educational institutions. This examination is conducted through the dual lenses of process and content. The article argues that successful change leadership in school settings necessitates several key steps: identifying the need for change, engaging stakeholders to acknowledge this need, structuring the change process, fostering stakeholder commitment, implementing and sustaining change through robust planning and oversight, and nurturing individual and organizational capabilities to enable problem-solving and solution generation. Moreover, it challenges the notion that change is solely a top-down endeavour, asserting that leadership is predominantly a social practice or process rather than merely a charismatic display.

Keywords: Change leadership, policy implementation, process issues, content issues

Introduction

Change, as the adage goes, is the only constant in every facet of human existence. Nowhere is this truer than in human organization, particularly within education. A profound comprehension and adept navigation of change leadership are paramount in any organization. Holman et al. (2007) assert that the ever-evolving societal trends within which organizations operate exert significant pressures for change in organizational practices. These trends encompass rapid advancements in information and communication technologies, heightened emphasis on democratic principles and education levels, increased global mobility, conflicting demands from various stakeholders, challenges in maintaining work-life balance, declining community engagement, and shifts in family and social dynamics (Dumas et al., 2018).

In a school system, leadership involves guiding teachers and students to improve the education process and achieve goals at all levels. In the Nigerian context, leaders in primary schools, secondary schools, and universities are called head teachers, principals, and vice-chancellors, respectively. Their educational leadership roles extend beyond managerial tasks, encompassing the educational system's advancement, creating an enabling environment for job satisfaction and professional development, and implementing policies aligned with education system objectives. Unfortunately, factors such as corruption, lack of accountability, social reorientation, and economic hardships threaten the roles of school leaders to function to total capacity, thereby adversely affecting the overall performance of students, especially in public schools. Several authors (Saint et al., 2013; Mohammed & Gbenu, 2017) have decried the poor performance of students at all levels. While Saint noted poor teaching and learning

reflected in the “labour market absorption and employers’ assessment of graduates”, Mohammed and Gbenu confirmed a substantial deterioration of quality education offered by higher education institutions in recent time due to poor quality leadership.

Against this background, there is an exacerbated need for change leadership. Amidst these complexities, many conventional leadership models must be revised to address the constant, rapid, and multifaceted changes. Even the venerable 'great man theory' of the 1840s is being scrutinized, as leaders must adapt their approaches to align with contemporary realities (Ahn et al., 2014). This scenario underscores the Nigerian educational system’s need for innovative strategies to reach its educational goals.

Change leadership has evolved to encompass a broader scope, transcending individual and group outcomes to focus on organizational objectives. Cawsey et al. (2012) posit that organizational change occurs through a nuanced understanding of human relationships intertwined with organizational outcomes. In this exploration, we delve into the following main objectives:

- Concept and Critical Facets of Change Leadership
- Educational Policies and Challenges of Implementation in Nigeria
- Impact of Change Leadership on the Nigerian Educational System
- Focus of Change Leadership through Policy Implementation: Process Issues (the 'how') and Content Issues (impacts on organizational effectiveness)
- Conclusion and Recommendations

Concept and Critical Facets of Change Leadership

Change leadership involves guiding individuals, teams, or organizations through significant transitions or transformations, implementing strategic changes to achieve specific goals, or adapting to new circumstances. These circumstances may stem from internal factors such as organizational restructuring or external factors like shifts in market dynamics or technological advancements. Metcalf (2023) defines change leadership as a management style that underscores the importance of organizational improvement and adaptability. In essence, it entails approaching organizational change with enthusiasm and a growth mindset.

Change leadership has three fundamental elements: adapting organizational practices to environmental or market changes, preparing for unexpected scenarios, and leveraging trending technologies. Unlike change management, which is typically tactical and often associated with specific projects having defined start and end dates, change leadership is often an ongoing process. It is a necessary skill within and outside change management projects (Akpoveta, 2019).

In 2012, Higgs and Rowland defined change leadership as follows: "Change leadership is the ability to influence and enthuse others through personal advocacy, vision and drive, and to access resources to build a solid platform for change." However, given the volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity in the world around us, Akpoveta (2019) proposed a new paradigmatic definition: “Change Leadership is the ability to influence and inspire action in others and respond with vision and agility during periods of growth, disruption, or uncertainty to bring about the necessary change”.

Throughout these definitions, certain features emerge that are central to change leadership or the characteristics of change leaders. Change leadership entails vision and direction, effective communication, change management, adaptability, empowerment, and continuous improvement. Akpoveta (2019) summarized the core skills required of a change leader to include the ability to:

- Lead and influence others, including peers and other leaders
- Anticipate and respond to change with agility
- Build and sustain momentum while remaining focused amid disruption
- Communicate effectively and collaborate with others
- Foster trust and demonstrate empathy by prioritizing people
- Identify and overcome barriers to change, maintaining focus on the bigger picture
- Establish the vision and engage others in its pursuit
- Foster cohesion among teams and colleagues, motivating and empowering them
- Be willing to take risks and demonstrate creativity, innovation, and decisiveness (Akpoveta, 2019, p. 2)

However, all these skills can be displayed within the purview of the policies in place and to the extent permissible by the policies. In other words, organizational policies or other factors, to a great extent, shape and define the leaders' boundaries. Leithwood and Azah (2016) call these other factors "forces." According to them, these forces include "constraints and opportunities provided by the province, district cultures that may have deep historical roots, and strong and sometimes contradictory community expectations" (Leithwood & Azah, 2016, p.11). In Nigeria, the amount of students' achievements often measures leadership success.

Meanwhile, only a little power and autonomy are left for the regional or zonal education authorities to define how to achieve students' success contextually. Regrettably, Galway et al. (2013) cited examples where school principals were charged with defending or taking responsibility for questionable decisions to which they had no input. Aside from this global disconnect between the policy implementers and formulators, in Nigeria, specific challenges stand in the way of implementing policies for school innovations.

Educational Policies and Implementation Challenges in Nigeria

Nigeria is the most populous African country, with over 229 million people, according to the United Nations (UN) 2024 Revision of World Population Prospects (UN, 2024). The National Education Policy formulation is the primary role of the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education as well as ensuring quality control in all levels of educational. The federal, state, and local governments are responsible for governance. Yaro (2018) noted that education, being on the legislative concurrent list, implies that the states are allowed to amend the federal education law when needed to suit their various states' education laws. This aimed to ensure that quality education was attained in each federation state. However, the central government controls the major sources of resource generation and allocation, negatively impacting the perceived state autonomy in adjusting the educational laws to suit them.

As a member of various international protocols like the UN Convention, and in meeting with the Nigerian educational needs, specific policies are formulated to solve a particular identified problem. Some of these policies, according to Ogunode and Adah (2020), include "the Child Act (2003), Universal Basic Education Act (2004), National Policy on HIV and AIDS for the Education Sector in Nigeria (2005), National Gender Policy (2006), National School Health Policy (2006), the Safe School Initiative (SSI) in Nigeria (2014), National Policy on Inclusive Education in Nigeria (2016) and National Home Grown School Feeding Programme (2016)" (p. 8).

The scope of this article does not cover the details of each of these policies. However, it concentrates only on the policy implementation and challenges faced by the various stakeholders in education at regional, state, local, and zonal levels for improved innovation in the Nigerian education system. Ogbonnanya (2010) defines policy implementation as carrying out the policy formulated in concrete terms. It implies systematically executing

programs, policies, and projects (Ogunode & Ahaotu, 2020). These and other factors determine educational policy implementation in Nigeria: the capacity of the implementer, the number of available teachers, the poor infrastructural facilities, lack of funds, the political will, and the level of monitoring and evaluation system available (Ogunode & Adah, 2020).

Regrettably, Nigeria, as a developing country, suffers specific uncommon challenges in its educational policy implementation, negatively impacting school innovation. Adeniyi (2015) pointed out that the main aim of designing educational policies was to offer sound knowledge and adaptation strategies to the citizens in a larger society. However, certain factors stand in the way of implementation, adversely impacting the overall aim of the policy. In addition to the problem of not including local and community impulses caused by the over-centralization of the federal government during policy formulation, several human, structural, and systemic challenges stand in the way of policy implementation. These challenges range from inadequate funding, infrastructural facilities, institutional corruption, lack of political will, insecurity, lack of continuity in commitment to policy implementation, political instability, poor policy formulation, and above all, poor relationships between policy designers and policy implementers (Yaro, 2018; Ige, & Fasakin, 2024; Kingdon & Maekae, 2013).

Impacts of Change Leadership on the Nigerian Educational System

Despite the already identified challenges and weaknesses of the current educational policies, there are numerous opportunities and prospects for enhancing the contribution of educational policy to national development in Nigeria through change leadership. It is crucial to focus on the following areas:

Increased Investment in Education: Given that insufficient funding is one of the significant obstacles to policy implementation in Nigeria, change leadership requires the government to prioritize education funding and allocate a more significant portion of the national budget to the educational sector. This will ensure the provision of adequate resources for infrastructure and human capital development (capacity building) at various educational levels. Beyond meeting UNESCO's recommended minimum of 26% of the national budget allocation to education (Ohaegbulem & Chijioke, 2023), Yaro (2018) suggested that personnel responsible for utilizing these funds should be trained in fiscal discipline to prevent misappropriation.

Curriculum Review and Innovation: As Holman et al. (2017) noted, the ever-evolving societal trends within which organizations operate exert significant pressures for change in organizational practices. These trends include rapid advancements in information and communication technologies, a heightened emphasis on democratic principles and education levels, increased global mobility, conflicting demands from various stakeholders, challenges in maintaining work-life balance, declining community engagement, and shifts in family and social dynamics (Dumas et al., 2018). Change leadership aims to stay attuned to societal needs. Therefore, it is essential to continuously review and update the curriculum at all educational levels to make it more relevant and responsive to the needs of the modern workforce and society. Oroma and Orlunga (2023) asserted that through change leadership, introducing Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education and integrating digital literacy into the curriculum can better prepare students for the future.

Public-Private Partnerships: Given the government's shortcomings in education, private ownership and administration of schools have flourished in Nigeria. Change leadership aims to achieve an effective educational system through collaboration between the government and private sector organizations. Yaro (2018) cautioned that the contributions of relevant education stakeholders, including community members and Non-Governmental

Organizations (NGOs), particularly regarding funding, should be addressed. For instance, many affluent individuals in the community are always ready to contribute to uplifting the education sector to achieve academic excellence.

Alliance with international practices: The focus on change leadership can also leverage standard practices beyond Nigeria's shores. Oroma and Orlunga (2023) recommended adopting an indigenous education system modeled after those in Asian countries while avoiding ideas alien to African (Nigerian) culture, as they are bound to fail. For a well-developed educational system in Nigeria, change leaders can balance addressing immediate community needs and adhering to federally formulated policies to accelerate student achievement and school innovation.

In all, a change leader in school should focus on two things: leading the change in school for innovation through policy implementation. These two things are what Dumas & Beinecke (2018) call **process issues**, which is how to bring about the change, and **content issues**, that is, the impact of the change.

Process Issues (the How) of Change Leadership

The process aspect of change leadership involves the actions taken to implement an intended change (Dumas & Beinecke, 2018). According to these authors, these actions occur at the external environment, firm, and individual levels. It is important to note that in education, various federal, state, and local government policies, as well as numerous activities, impact the external environment of the school system. However, this article focuses solely on the actions required to implement changes within the school system and employees' responses to such efforts. Cawsey et al. (2012) identify the following stages for effecting change: “awakening, mobilization, acceleration, and institutionalization, which form an iterative process to bring about change.”

These stages, according to Cawsey et al (2012), involve “building and energizing the need for change, providing frameworks for leading change, navigating change through formal structures and systems”, managing organizational politics and culture, influencing internal stakeholders and managing recipients of change, becoming adept at leading change, action planning and implementation, sustaining change, measuring change, and designing effective control systems. To achieve these improvements in the Nigerian education system, change leaders should identify the disconnect between policy and current societal needs. For instance, the 6-3-3-4 education system introduced in 1983 was replaced with the 9-3-4 system in 2004. This change addressed policy implementation challenges such as infrastructure shortages, teacher training and quality, and educational equity (NaijaCurrent, 2023).

To provide further clarity on the change leadership process, Moran and Brightman (2011) assert that the focus of change management is shifting from the change itself to the people it impacts. In essence, change leaders should align work behavior with the reasons, locations, individuals involved, and methods of change implementation. This approach helps leaders avoid resistance to change and enhances their ability to manage organizational change effectively. In addition, Gill (2013) presents the spectacle model of change leadership, which comprises cognitive, spiritual, emotional, and behavioural dimensions and requirements. The study emphasizes that effective change leadership encompasses vision, values, strategy, empowerment, motivation, and inspiration. Without these elements, leadership efforts can be ‘misguided or even detrimental to the organization’ (Gill, 2013, p. 312).

In school settings, innovative and change leaders must cultivate a culture of organizational change that benefits the school and the individuals within the school system. According to Alimo-Metcalfe and Alban-Metcalfe (2015), cultural change programs should anticipate and consider factors influencing employees' ability to adapt.

The approach to change should emphasize service and enable others to lead themselves in alignment with the school leaders' vision.

In a different perspective, Higgs and Rowland (2015) proposed that successful change is predicated on the assumption of complexity rather than linearity. As Gilley et al. (2019) described, change is complex, uncertain, and evolutionary, characterized by continuous growth and development. Their study established a relationship between leadership behaviour and effectiveness in driving change. They concluded that leaders with diverse abilities to motivate, communicate, and build teams effectively lead change.

Different schools of thought offer various perspectives in summarizing change leadership through policy implementation from process issues. Behaviourists advocate for change leaders to “recognize the need for policy change, set goals, communicate direction, formulate a change strategy, involve others, motivate, provide support, and create an organizational context conducive to implementing the policy” (Dumas & Beinecke, 2018, p. 11). Situational leadership theorists reject the notion of a one-size-fits-all leadership style. Instead, they argue that the most effective leadership theory, building upon transformational leadership theory, is for change leaders to inspire followers, foster identification with the leader's mission, and evoke followers' emotional engagement and desire for intellectual stimulation (Hayes, 2010, pp 162).

Content Issues (the Impact) of Change Leadership in Policy Implementation

The content issue of change leadership revolves around assessing the success or failure of change efforts and their impact on organizational effectiveness. Dumas and Beinecke (2018) view the content issue as the process through which an organization establishes its long-term relationship with its environment, defining its overall character, mission, and direction. While some researchers (Burns, 2011) question why change initiatives fail, others (Cummings & Worley, 2005; French & Bell, 1999) propose successful models such as organizational development and emergent change. However, Burns (2011) warns that only some approaches can address the diverse range of change situations that may arise.

Metaphorically, various analogies, such as organisms, political systems, and machines, have been used to elucidate how organizational change functions (Cameron & Green, 2012). Emergent change theorists advocate for change leadership in schools to evolve alongside the institution, with continuous adaptability and flexibility, albeit punctuated by intermittent bursts. The system should promote democratic processes, fostering self-learning even through failure. While advocating for flexibility and continuous reinvention, Anderson (2015) cautions against both “small-scale incremental changes and large-scale radical changes.” Therefore, change leaders must assume roles such as the edgy catalyst, visionary motivator, measured connector, tenacious implementer, and thoughtful architect (Cameron & Green, 2012) to enable behaviour rather than dictate it. Dumas and Beinecke (2018) add another perspective by suggesting that directive, top-down change management approaches that seek to control the process are less effective.

Additionally, Higgs and Rowland (2011) propose five processes for effective change leadership:

- Creating the need for change, i.e., establishing the necessity for change.
- Engaging others to recognize the need, i.e., involving others in understanding the need for change.
- Creating the structured change, i.e., formulating a well-organized plan for change.
- Engage others in the change process and build commitment, i.e., involving others throughout and fostering commitment.

- Implementing and sustaining change, i.e., executing change with comprehensive plans, monitoring progress, and conducting reviews.
- Facilitating and developing capability, i.e., encourages individuals to discover their solutions to problems and fosters their development (Higgs & Rowland (2011, p. 314).

These processes demand humility and strong determination. Transformational and servant leaders envision changes that benefit the organization and its members. They emphasize power sharing, empowerment, and setting goals that inspire others while providing necessary resources for personal growth. The concept underlying this approach is that organizational change is collectively achieved when individuals are supported in their self-development. In contrast to "heroic" leaders who make decisions unilaterally, Sarros et al. (2018) argue that these leaders empower others, enabling the organization to thrive even after their departure (p. 146), thus promoting innovation beyond the leader's tenure.

In 2016, Siren et al. studied "How do harmonious passion and obsessive passion moderate the influence of a CEO's change-oriented leadership on company performance?" Their findings revealed that change-oriented leadership accompanied by harmonious passion enhances organizational performance, whereas change-oriented leadership accompanied by obsessive passion does not lead to higher organizational performance. Therefore, for sustained change, a shift in mindset is necessary. This includes staying attuned to the realities of the environment, building coalitions, transferring ownership to a working team, cultivating perseverance, and recognizing the contributions of all individuals (Kanter in Cameron & Green, 2012, pp. 188-189). Effective change communication is crucial, enabling employees to participate actively in the implementation process.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, change leadership is a complex concept with no one-size-fits-all approach to implementation. Unfortunately, change has often been perceived as a top-down process involving controlling and micromanaging every detail, leading to a misconception that change is manageable. Change leaders must navigate this complexity by striking a balance in their actions, recognizing that each environment presents unique challenges and opportunities for change. Considering the volatility of the education system in Nigeria in terms of leadership instability, school leaders are encouraged to focus on the stated objectives and policies of the school instead of acting a script written by their paymasters at the expense of the common good.

Empirically based policy change is needed in the context of school innovations. Policy change should be continuous according to the community's needs, neither radical nor sluggish. The key to successfully navigating policy change is maintaining an open rather than closed system and keeping the organization operating on the edge of chaos—neither too stable nor too chaotic (Dumas & Beinecke, 2018). Emphasis should be placed on fostering a culture of change, developing teams, and supporting individuals affected by policy change. It is highly recommended that Nigerian school leaders create a system that supports individual difficulties adjusting to change.

Finally, leadership is not about individual heroism but rather a collective endeavour. It is a social practice or process rather than a charismatic activity. With no single correct approach to leading change, it is crucial to consider cultural and organizational factors that induce and drive change rather than solely focusing on impediments. Maintaining a positive mindset devoid of personal fame and being open to accepting change are catalysts for innovation and positive transformation. There should be opportunities for top-bottom and bottom-up change, engaging employees and empowering them with accountability while fostering an enabling environment.

Both leaders and team members should respect structured systems, and a stable blueprint or action plan should be communicated to all involved. This plan serves as a reference point for everyone, with occasional adjustments made sparingly. Accountability becomes inherent in daily duties when a stable plan is in place. However, if employees are still determining what lies ahead, they may overly rely on leaders for further actions, thus limiting the change process.

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